

School-Based Management Practices and Performance Among Elementary and Secondary Schools of Davao City Division

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Abstract. The purpose of the study was to estimate performance-difference of School Based Management performance among Elementary and Secondary Schools given practices from School Year 2017-2018 to 2019-2020. Descriptive-inferential using test of difference was used as the design of the study. Elementary and Secondary Schools' stakeholders were the respondents of the study using secondary data which was generated from APAT tool. Results revealed that most Elementary and Secondary Schools are in the Maturing Level Stage of SBM Practices, while Schools displayed a good extent of implementation given performance indicators, nutritional status and English and Filipino Proficiency. Moreover, using Kruska-Wallis H-test, it found no empirical evidence to show significant difference on the performance of Elementary and Secondary schools given principles and indicators of SBM level of practices and likewise when measured with School's Performance Indicators, Nutritional Status and English and Filipino Proficiency. The study concludes that Schools are in mature level, and displayed good performance for the last three school years 2017-2018 to 2019-2020. It is recommended that a review on existing policy on School Improvement Planning, Review, Monitoring and Assessment may be done, and a restructure and reeducation of SBM key persons such as the role of PSDS and School Heads given respective KRAs to clearly appropriate the roles and responsibilities for a correct deliverables, and likewise, Teachers need to be coached on the tasks given as School's SBM Principle Chair and member of the committee through the leadership of the School Heads and PSDS's technical assistance, and may lessen the intertwining of tasks to make focused on the main goal of SBM, that is to improve learning outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. School Based Management 2. Performance Indicators 3. three School Years

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1. Introduction

The persistent widening gap in performances among schools is alarming. Also, ongoing collaborative partnerships parents and guardians show in private schools are different from what happens in the public schools. Moreover, education and training play a unique role in human capital development that tends to have a considerable effect on the economic development of nations (Koc Bastas, 2019). Thus, schools become the hub for training and graduating enrollees. At the school level, some activities capitalized as either school manage-

ment or operation issues as denominators of school effectiveness and efficiency. The formative years of future leaders, technocrats and indeed human capital needed for accelerated economic development is contingent on foundations of education and schooling. Given the premise, School-based Management is still everyone's business in the entire learning system. Although the challenges of improving education at all levels necessitate the participation of various stakeholders in the school system (Chinenye Victor, 2018). Several factors have either been accused or excused at one point in time or the other. Schooling and learning outcomes are at the crossroads across countries. In Ghana, (Abreh, 2017) stated that current state of stakeholder involvement and participation in school-based management within selected communities in these two districts are not well coordinated. There was a limited collaboration between the entire SMC membership and the schools they serve. Additionally, committee planning and implementation issues were significant concerns. Thus, effective school-based management is dependent upon the principal's capacity to facilitate good instructional practices. However, principals need to adjust their leadership practices to school contextual demand and adaptation to contexts result in the varied developments of teacher capacities in schools, corresponding with the types of principal leadership adopted (Lee Chiu, 2017). In the Philippines, DepEd thrust that decentralizes the decision-making from the Central Office and field offices to individual schools to enable them to better respond to their specific education needs. Recent report revealed that schools report, that they are not yet implementing many of the key aspects of this system. Moreover, parents and local communities still play a very limited role in decision-making and in holding schools accountable. Given the ever-increasing amounts of resources that schools now control and the need to give them more flexibility over

how to use those funds, this note argues that the role of representative school governing councils could be expanded and efforts made by DepEd to increase awareness among parents and education stakeholders of the useful role they could play in supporting school-based management. It is in this juncture that, the current school year is about to end the last cycle of the three year School Improvement Plan (SIP) and it is about to start reviewing the past three years performances to come up with sound prioritization for implementation of the next three year cycle. Thus, it is empirical to assess the performance of the schools in Davao City Division for the past three school years 2017-2018, 2018-2019 and 2019-2020, in terms of SBM Practices and the Performance with respect to improving of learning outcomes. This assessment and evaluation research will pave the way through giving evidence to show how the schools performing and what interventions can be done to improve performances of learning outcomes. This advocates the enhancement of the next cyclical planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Thus, this research paper is proposed.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature— School-based management (SBM) emphasizes leadership and governance to achieve shared educational goals, responsive to diverse environments. Effective leadership is crucial, as demonstrated by research showing that effective principals significantly raise student achievement (Szachowicz, 2014). Collaboration among stakeholders, guided by Department of Education mandates, ensures relevant curriculum development and instructional strategies tailored to learners' needs (Camilo Westin, 2019; Sanaghan, 2009).

Curriculum and instruction are designed to meet the diverse needs of all learners, ensuring continuous improvement in learning outcomes. Localized curricula, developed with community input, make learning meaningful and applicable to real-life contexts (Florio-Ruane, 2002;

Bigham Riney, 2014). Regular assessment and community involvement help maintain relevance and effectiveness in educational programs.

Accountability is a key component of SBM, with performance monitoring systems collaboratively developed by school communities (Hutt Polikoff, 2020; Usman, 2016). This includes regular assessments and feedback mechanisms to address gaps and recognize achievements.

Resource management in schools involves transparent and collaborative processes, ensuring resources are effectively allocated and utilized (Börü, 2018; Faubert, 2019). Schools must practice regular resource inventories and involve stakeholders in decision-making to support continuous educational improvement.

Performance indicators, including enrollment, promotion, graduation, and dropout rates, provide essential data for evaluating school effectiveness (DM 892 S 2020). Nutritional status is another critical factor, with research highlighting the importance of accurate maternal perceptions of children's health (Lizama-González, Ramos-Ramírez, Lozano-Contreras, 2020; Wheeler, 2017). Reading proficiency is also crucial, as it underpins holistic development and lifelong learning (Kingsley Nyarko, 2018).

In conclusion, SBM principles guide the effective governance and operation of schools, ensuring that all stakeholders contribute to the sustainable development of human resources through improved educational outcomes.

1.2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—To make more realistic in probing the claimed hypothesis based on the current concerns of the proposed study, the researcher considered several theories that is related and relevant to augment sound discussion take off. These theories are perpendicularly upright to satisfy the assumptions of the claim of the study, and the most likely to fit the concept of the study which found to be more realistic in terms

of transforming these concepts to reality and can be felt by the stakeholders of the learning communities. Being practical and utilitarian school of thought, the theory of pragmatism has influenced education to the maximum extent. It has tried overcoming the limitations of other schools like idealism and naturalism and has influenced the world to a great extent (Pratima Chamling Rai, 2020). Pragmatic means the quality of dealing with the problem in a sensible way that suits the conditions that really exists, rather than following a fixed theories, ideas or rules. Pragmatism is an educational philosophy that says education should be teaching students the things that are practical for life and encourages them to grow into better people. Many famous educators including John Dewey, William James were pragmatists. Pragmatists believe in the idea of practical learning i.e. education should apply to the real world. Thus, this paper examines pragmatism, its contribution to education. It further discusses how the basic principles of pragmatism can be applied in learning thereby making the process of teaching-learning more effective (Szachowicz, 2014). Moreover, pragmatism in the current days of education, Florio-Ruane (2002) as quoted by (Monk, p. 2002), serves that efforts to generalize the results of teacher effectiveness studies are often thwarted by the contextual, local, and situated nature of teaching and learning (Florio-Ruane, 2002). Such challenges met along the way, needs to be reversed and lessen the burden to overcome and turn into more realistic and practical. One of the most noteworthy education trends in recent years has been the increase in demands placed on principals. With numerous mandates to implement, a move toward decentralized decision making that puts more authority in their hands, and an education landscape that is rapidly changing including more pervasive technology and evolving student demographics the challenges of effective school leadership have never been greater

Fig. 1. Pictorial representation showing the concept-variables under study

(Szachowicz, 2014). It's not an exaggeration to say that the success of the current round of education reform initiatives will be largely dictated by the success of our principals. Clearly, the wisdom of the philosophers is alive until the advancement of technologies in these current days. Education continually improve time to time and as the need and urgency has to be addressed (Pratima Chamling Rai, 2020), strategies for programs, projects and activities have been redirected to fit into the current and pressing needs, addressing the learners' advancement transformation into life-long skills improvement (Bhandari, 2021). Therefore, it is in this sense that theory of pragmatism, become more prac-

tical in dealing with the conduct, analysis, interpretation and drawing implications from the data gathered. Application of the theory is further discussed its content through the context of the conceptual framework that is shown in Figure 1 below. The concept of the study is represented by the dependent and independent variables below. Figure 1 gives us the pictorial representation of the concept under study. Contention of the proponent is to assess the performance of Binugao District Schools in the implementation of School Based Management which are evident in to practices for the past three consecutive School Years 2017-2018 to 2019-2020.

The dependent variable School Based Management Performance Davao City Division Schools is estimated through the School's indicators of Improving Learning Outcomes. These are the enrollment rate, drop-out rate, survival rate, graduation rate, retention rate, promotion rate, completion rate and the proficiency level. Moreover, nutritional status and reading proficiency are also included in this parameter. This information will be taken in a form of secondary data where schools are archiving. On the other hand, independent variables, are the predictors that analyzes the difference of SBM Practices given the SBM Performance amongst schools. This covers the four principles of the SBM, namely Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Instruction, Accountability and Continuous Improvement and Resource Management. These principles do have respective indicators to

measure the practices given evidence from the conducted programs, projects and activities. In this manner, the practices are measured and will be compared across past three years, given the assumption of the school's performance. Since education is preparation for life, the theory of pragmatism that claims to have a sound contribution in the educational learning system, has to be continuously be argued and be proven in this study. Education is preparation for life. The results of the study will make a way to share to the knowledge community that school-based management is a sound tool and instrument to continuously improve quality education delivery. It idealizes the activity on the basis of its consequence over time frame. In short, it conceptualizes an inference on the basis of changed or changing needs, circumstances and places. For the creation of new values, activity and ex-

perience are essential. Education should therefore, provide physical, intellectual, moral and aesthetic activities as the media for the creation of new values. All round development of the individual is also an important aim of education. The individual develops physical-ly, mentally, socially and aesthetically. Lastly, the theory and practice of education is based on two main principles, namely (i) Education should have a social function and (ii) Education should provide real life experience to the child. Every continuous experience or activity is educative

and all education in fact, resides in having such experience. But continuous growth in experience is not the whole education. Education is something more. It is constant reorganizing or reconstructing of experience.

1.3. Research Questions—This study aimed to estimate the performance-difference of School Based Management performance among Elementary and Secondary Schools given practices from School Year 2017 - 2018 to 2019 - 2020. Thus, sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the level of School-Based Management Practices among Elementary and Secondary Schools during SY 2017-2018 to 2019-2020 in terms of;
 - (1) Leadership and Governance
 - (2) Curriculum and Instruction
 - (3) Accountability and Continuous Improvement
 - (4) Resource Management
- (2) What is the extent of SBM Performance among Elementary and Secondary Schools across three School Years?
- (3) Is there a significant difference among Elementary and Secondary Schools' SBM Performance when analyzed across three School Years? 4. How much is the magnitude of difference across three School Years?

1.4. Scope and Limitation—The intended output of the study is to produce sound innovations that could be a good input as intervention-activities for every cyclical planning among the schools of the school of the Division of Davao City. These interventions can be a good take-off for implementation and im-proving the strategies based on the objectives and targets of the school's plan. Innovative processes in appreciating the articulation of indicators based on standards shall be generated through a process steps, using swim-lane and flow charts of which reflecting the details and each steps will have the activities that is good as interventions for every project. Such process steps

2. Methodology

Participants of the study were the internal and external stakeholders of the learning school communities. They are the School Heads, the SBM District / Cluster and School Coordinators, the teachers, parents and members of the School Governing Council.

2.1. Sampling—Probability sampling technique (Gujarati, 2004) was employed in the study. This specifically used stratified technique where this divides the population into smaller groups that don't overlap but represent the entire population. Given strata, a simple

random sampling was employed where, the proponent determined the sample size using the Raosoft sample size calculator, considering the estimated population size, confidence level and the margin of error. Table 1 below shows the figure:

Table 1. Stratified-random sampling at 95% confidence level and 5% error

Strata	Estimated Population	No. of Samples
School Head	144	105
SBM Coordinators	144	105
Total		210

Table shows the number of samples from each group where the proponent will look for to answer the survey. Thus, expecting the normality of distribution of samples, from a given estimated population.

2.2. *Data Collection*—To measure the SBM level of practices among Schools, the proponent will adopt the SBM APAT Tool, where its contents is composed of SBM principles and indicators (attached as Survey Instrument of the study) namely, Leadership and Governance with four sets of indicators; Curriculum and Instruc-

tion which listed ten indicators; Accountability and Continuous Improvement and Resource Management with five indicators respectively. These principles were measured by the respondents by reflecting a check (/) mark on the column that corresponds their answers given the statement-indicators listed. Using a 4-Likert rating scale (Louis Cohen L. M., 2007), re-sponses shall be treated through a score, scale, description and interpretation. Details are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameters in Estimating SBM Level of Practices

Score	Scale	Description	Interpretation
4	3.26 – 4.00	Excellent	[tl]Refers to that School’s SBM Level of Practice/Extent is in ADVANCED Stage Level
3	2.51 – 3.25	Very Good	[tl]Refers to that School’s SBM Level of Practice/Extent is in MATURING Stage Level
2	1.76 – 2.50	Good	[tl]Refers to that School’s SBM Level of Practice/Extent is in DEVELOPING Stage Level
1	1.00 – 1.75	Better	[tl]Refers to that School’s SBM Level of Practice/Extent is in BEGINNING Stage Level

This was the tool to generate primary data, while, measuring the SBM Level of Performance for the past three school years, list of

indicators of learners’ outcomes are presented in Table 3, thus.

To ensure that the adopted research instrument fits to the desired output of the study, content shall still be subjected to panel of experts,

such as the SBM School Coordinators and thus, results will be analyzed through reliability test Cronbach Alpha .05 level of significance (Gu-

Table 3. Improvement of Learning Outcomes

Performance Indicators	Nutritional Status	Reading Proficiency in English, Filipino, and MTB-MLE
1. Enrollment Rate	1. Normal	1. Independent
2. Drop-out Rate	2. Wasted	2. Instructional
3. Survival Rate	3. Severely Wasted	3. Frustration
4. Graduation Rate	4. Obese	4. Non-Readers
5. Retention Rate		
6. Completion Rate		
7. Proficiency Level (SF 6)		

jarati, 2004). Further, measure scale adopted was based on Regional guidelines in appreciating SBM Performance-validation through a scale of 5, 10 and 15 respectively.

2.3. *Ethical Issues*—This study strictly observed to the ethical principles governing in the conduct of research. Principles like informed consent, confidentiality and anonymity, and free from risks were observed in this study. Informed consent was sought by the researcher informing the participant his role in the study. The participant was requested to affix his signature showing his willingness to take part in the study. Another principle is confidentiality and anonymity. It was ensured that no identifying marks was divulged or released about the profile of the participant. Also, the safety of the participant was ensured.

2.4. *Data Analysis Plan*—To answer the statement of the problem posed, this study used appropriate statistical tool that sufficed the requirements of the data analysis. This answered problems 1 and 2, (Tasiran, 2004) stated that mean scores and corresponding descriptive in-

terpretation shall be employed to answer the level of SBM practices, while percentage distribution were used to determine the indicators of SBM performance across three school years. Addressing the queries posed in statement problem number 3, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) (Lavery, 2018) was used to determine the significant difference among Davao City Division Schools across (Lavery, 2018) three school years and, if found it significant, magnitude of difference were calculated using post-hoc analysis. All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations will then follow when results yield. In addition, to abide with the ethics policy in research (Marguerite G. Lodico, 2006), the proponent ensures that all selected sample-respondents were subjected for an orientation giving them the idea on the significance of the study, likewise letter of informed consent shall be given with the objective that the respondents are protected under anonymity policy.

3. Results and Discussion

The preceding presentations are the analysis, interpretations and discussions of the yielded results from the data gathered. This is shown through tabular and textual presentations aligned with the posed statement of the problem. Interpretations and discussions are based and anchored on the reviewed literature.

3.1. *On the SBM Level of Practices*—The study sought to answer the SBM Level of Practices among Elementary and Secondary Schools across three School Years, from 2017-2018 to 2019-2020. As depicted in Table 3, results shown that Elementary and Secondary Schools’ SBM Level of practice given the four principles, results aggregate to have been in maturing stage across three school years, with a mean and standard deviation score of (M=2.757; sd=.171) for Leadership and Governance; (M=2.719; sd=.396), for Curriculum and Instruction; (M=2.719; sd= 1.000) for Accountability and Continuous Improvement; and

(M=2.744; sd= 3.000) for Management of Resources respectively. The yielded results given the scores generated during Division SBM validation found to be in support of the Schools’ SBM level of practices for each principles’ indicators that SBM level of practices are generally in maturing stage, for it can be clearly observed that the details of each indicator for every principle were not practically delivered as directed by each principle’s standards. Most if not all schools are still in the process of reappreciating the assumptions and re-requirements given the standards of each level of practices across three school years.

Table 4. School Year Principles and SBM Level of Practice in Elementary and Secondary Education

Level	School Year	Principles	Mean (\bar{x})	sd	SBM Level of Practice
Elementary	2017-2018	Leadership and Governance	2.757	.171	Maturing Stage
	2018-2019	Curriculum and Instruction	2.719	.396	Maturing Stage
	2019-2020				
Secondary		Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.719	1.000	Maturing Stage
		Management of Resources	2.744	3.000	Maturing Stage

The importance of school leadership is clearly seen in research and thus reflects school-based management. Leadership matters, and this is shared by authors including a recent study by Gregory F. Branch, Eric A. Hanushek, and Steven G. Rivkin. They reported in *Education Next* that a highly effective principal raises student achievement by between two and seven additional months of learning in a single school year (Szachowicz, 2014). These new principals may have been incredible teachers, but might not yet have the training, skills, and support in instructional leadership necessary to lead schoolwide achievement. Many veteran principals are stunned at the lack of training

given to new principals. Turnover remains a constant source of concern as well, says Sue Gendron, a former education commissioner in Maine (Monk, 1992). While this is crucially important for new principals, it is equally important that experienced principals have a chance for ongoing support. For inspiration, success-based teacher-induction models and implement equivalent programs for principals, consisting of professional learning covering key principles, in-person or virtual coaching, and collaboration with peers in a confidential setting. Moreover, curriculum delivery and instruction has to be relevant enough to the context of the learners to get a high chance of transforming the

learning into fullest of life skills (Florio-Ruane, 2002). As educational needs of students change in response to changing demographics, economic factors, workforce needs, and school accountability requirements, school leaders must continually monitor and adjust curricula and associated methods of instructional delivery to increase student learning. The analysis of student performance data is a critical component of curriculum decision-making processes, and the purpose of this study is to demonstrate an application of trend analysis techniques in making curriculum and instruction decisions using historical student performance data (Bigham Riney, 2014). The techniques are demonstrated in relation to a real school problem and are transferrable to similar problems facing other schools. Thus, CI indicates the roles and responsibilities of accountable persons and collective bodies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders, where in achievement of goals is recognized based on collaboratively developed performance accountability system where gaps are addressed through appropriate actions. In this context, it is interpreted that a community-accepted performance accountability, recognition and incentive system is being practiced. Moreover, this accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanism are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community (DM 377 S 2021). Given this accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanism, and information collection, and validation techniques and processes are inclusive collaboratively developed agreed. Participatory assessment of performance is done regularly with the community. Assessment results lessons learned serve as basis for feedback, technical assistance, recognition plan adjustment. Public accountability through information disclosure is a pillar of modern education reform efforts (Hutt Polikoff, 2020). Recent decades have

revealed a gap between promises and realities of accountability in education governance, as well as further afield. Despite efforts identifying and analyzing cautionary tales of accountability interventions (Fahey Köster, 2019), a systematic approach to support progressive improvements for managing accountability in complex education systems is yet to be widely adopted. Schools and other educational institutions are established, maintained and sustained essentially to achieve certain assured objectives. The goals of such establishment cannot be easily achieved without putting in place certain mechanisms towards ensuring the success of implementation of its policies and programmes. In the education system, one of the vital mechanisms to be put in place towards achieving the goals of the school and ensuring quality service delivery to the society is accountability (Usman, 2016). Some factors hindering accountability in the education system and strategies for improving accountability in the School System like regular supervision of schools, visionary leadership, effective communication, education auditing and adequate funding of the education sector to ensure efficient management and improve quality service delivery by the schools.

3.2. *On the extent of SBM Performance among Elementary and Secondary Schools across three School Years—*Meanwhile, addressing the posed statement problem number 2, table 4 presents the extent of Schools' Performance based on indicators, namely, the eight performance indicators, the English and Filipino Proficiency and Nutritional Status among Elementary and Secondary Schools during SY 2017-2018 to 2019-2020. Elementary and Secondary schools displayed good performance in general. It garnered a mean score and sd of 66.143; 8.697 for across performance indicators; a mean score of 11.647 and 2.080 (for English Proficiency) and mean score of 11.985 and sd of 2.349 (for Filipino Proficiency) and mean score of 30.667 and sd of 2.949 for nutritional

status across three school years. The results generated gives an impression that Elementary and Second-ary Schools delivered a satisfactory performance across indicators as provided by SBM standards, principle-indicators and the respective level of practices.

Table 5. Extent of SBM Performance among Elementary and Secondary Schools during SY 2017-2018 to 2019-2020

Elementary and Secondary School's Performance	Mean (\bar{x})	sd	SBM Extent Performance
Performance Indicator	66.143	8.698	Good
English Proficiency	11.647	2.081	Good
Filipino Proficiency	11.985	2.349	Good
Nutritional Status	30.667	2.950	Good

Measurements of nutritional status, usually based on the growth of children, have been suggested as potentially useful indicators of the health and welfare of communities, in addition to their value for screening individuals for curative treatment (F.Wheeler, 2017). It should be recognized that numerical scales and critical levels of indicators reflect social valuations (of 'bad' states or 'good' states) and are not simply technical descriptions of physiological states. Properly understood and employed, nutritional indicators could be used for the planning and evaluation of programmes, not only in the health sector, but in all areas concerned with social development. The purpose of reading is comprehension which means getting meaning from written text. Find out what else research tells us about the active process of constructing meaning, and how good readers consciously employing comprehension strategies (What Research Tells Us About Reading, Comprehension, and Comprehension Instruction, 2020). The ultimate goal of independent reading is to achieve reading proficiency, which facilitates knowledge acquisition and dissemination and leads to holistic development of the individual. When pupils at the basic level of education are proficient in reading, it makes learning an enjoyable activity, which fosters the drive to acquire more knowledge, and leads to the produc-

tion of a holistically developed human resource. This would effectively and eventually trigger national development, which lends support to the assumption that a reading nation is a developed nation. Independent reading simply refers to the ability of students to read on their own without anybody necessarily instructing them to do so. This also involves selecting books of interest, time as well as place to read, which is likely to have a positive influence on their reading comprehension and adoption of strategies aimed at enhancing reading strategies (Kingsley Nyarko, 2018, August 30).

3.3. *On the significant difference among Elementary and Secondary Schools' SBM Performance when analyzed across three School Years*—Tables 6, 7 and 8 shows the Levene's test of equality, Shapiro-Wilk and Kruskal-Wallis test. As part of the process of analysis, and before using any statistical inferencing tools, it is proper to check the test of assumptions using Levene's test. Results appeared to fail on the assumptions on equality of variance $p=0.945$), thus, proceeding to Shapiro-Wilk's test of normality of data, it revealed that data do not pass on the requirements for normality of distribution. This made the process of analysis use nonparametric test of analysis through Kruskal-Wallis H-test which is equally correct with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Table 6. Test for Equality of Variances (Levene’s)

F	df1	df2	p
0.057	2.000	108.000	0.945

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics

Overall Performance	
Valid	111
Shapiro-Wilk	0.906
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	.001

Table 8. Kruskal-Wallis Test

Factor	Statistic	df	p	η^2
Year	3.930	2	0.140	0.021

A Kruskal- Wallis H-Test was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the performance of the schools across three school years. Results revealed that there is no significant difference across Elementary and Secondary Schools’ SBM Performance when analyzed by three School Years, $H(2) = 3.93$, $p = .14$. Moreover, Cohen’s f was also used to determine the magnitude of effect using the years which showed that years have a small effect on the change of Elementary and Secondary Schools’ SBM Performance with $\eta^2 = .021$.

3.4. On the magnitude of difference across three School Years—There must be an added analysis that can be run based on data given to provide empirical evidence showing magnitude of difference. However, given table 6 revealed no significant difference, then no magnitude of

difference can be tested. However, when asked on the difference among Schools’ Performance indicators , Nutrition status, English Proficiency, and Filipino Proficiency of Elementary and Secondary Schools, Kruskal-Wallis H-test was used to determine the significant difference. Results shown in Table 7 that indicators for School’s Performance generated a value of $H(2) = 1.039$, $p = .595$; Nutritional Status of $H(2) = 3.186$, $p = .203$; English Proficiency of $H(2) = 1.953$, $p = .377$; and Filipino Proficiency of $H(2) = 4.062$, $p = .131$. This can be construed that all indicators found to be not significant amongst Elementary and Secondary schools. This is giving an impression that Schools’ Performance do not have significant difference for three school years when measured by the given performance standards indicators.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Given the results presented and discussed, the following conclusions and recommendations are derived.

4.1. Conclusions—

- (1) Elementary and Secondary Schools’ SBM Level of Practices are generally in maturing stage;

Table 9. Test of Magnitude of Difference

Indicators	Factor	Statistic	df	p-value
Performance	3 School Years	1.039	2	0.595
Nutritional Status	3 School Years	3.186	2	0.203
English Proficiency	3 School Years	1.953	2	0.377
Filipino Proficiency	3 School Years	4.062	2	0.131

- (2) Elementary and Secondary Schools’ Performance given Indicators are in very good extent of implementation;
- (3) Elementary and Secondary Schools’ SBM Performance do not differ when analyzed across three School Years 2017-2018 to 2019-2020; and
- (4) Elementary and Secondary Schools’ extent of implementation do not differ its magnitude when analyzed with performance indicators, nutritional status and proficiency in English and Filipino.

4.2. *Recommendations*—It is therefore recommended that, School Based Management in Elementary and Secondary Schools has to be revisited in terms of its implementation and operationalization given indicators and levels of practices with respect to each SBM Principles. Thus,

- (1) Review on existing policy on School Improvement Planning, Review, Monitoring and Assessment;
- (2) Restructure and reeducation of SBM key Persons such as the role of PSDS and School Heads given respective KRAs to clearly appropriate the roles and responsibilities for a correct deliverables;
- (3) Teachers need to be coached on the tasks given as School’s SBM Principle Chair and member of the committee through the leadership of the School Heads and PSDS’s technical assistance;
- (4) Lessen the intertwining of tasks to make focused on the main goal of SBM, that is to improve learning outcomes.

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